

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY-BASED HEALTH CARE

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Abstract. *Computer tools are considered as diagnostic equipment. The main applications of computers in medicine include hospital information system, data analysis in medicine, laboratory computing of medical images, computer-assisted medical decision making, critically ill patient care, computer therapy, and so on. Health Informatics - aims to organize and manage information in support of patient care, biomedical research and education through computers and information networks.*

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Computers are currently being used in hospitals to track patients, process and distribute test results, ensure that appropriate medications are used, apply for insurance claims, and record patient outcomes as a measure of the quality of care. Computers are becoming more and more popular every day among a wide range of people. With the advent of microcomputers in the late seventies and the subsequent increase in their performance in the eighties, computers made their way to our homes. Computers have undoubtedly revolutionized our entire way of life. Computer technologies have a huge application in the field of medicine, where they have the greatest social impact[1].

Computer tools are considered as an integral part of diagnostic equipment. The main applications of computers in medicine include hospital information system, data analysis in medicine, laboratory computing of medical images, computer-assisted medical decision making, critically ill patient care, computer therapy, and so on.

Medical informatics is a rapidly developing discipline. It aims to organize and manage information in support of patient care, biomedical research and education through computers and information networks [2]. A computerized hospital information system can establish consistent standards for data transmission and storage and track all transactions at all times. It provides easy access to valuable patient care information. Doctors can have direct access to all information about their patient using a computer. The hospital information system typically covers areas such as check-in, admission/transfer/discharge, billing, medical record, zip code, rooms, operating room schedule, warehouses/inventory, pharmacy, diet, biomedical care, payroll, bills, etc.

In order to promote the development of hospital information systems, it is necessary to improve research and development capabilities and the technical level. Building a hospital information system requires the analysis of a large amount of clinical data and pathoanatomical reports, as well as their complex processing. At present, hospitals, especially well-known and

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influential large hospitals, not only have many internal institutions and staff, but also have to face thousands of patients who enter the hospital every day, which requires the hospital to improve, error-free and standardized management. The computer information system is widely used in hospitals in registration fees, diagnosis and hospitalization, as well as in human resource management, medical care management and property management, thereby improving the overall management and service level of the hospital. In addition, the computer information system also plays an indispensable role in building hospital digital technology, medical work and medical education in hospitals, finding and sharing information about medical resources, and implementing

Computer technology has made the mathematical analysis of biological phenomena feasible, especially mathematical models of biological systems are of great importance. In the medical field (and especially in the drug market) is quite formalized, because based on globally accepted terminology. This creates good conditions for creating adequate data models and information flows. Over the previous years, a long way has been covered by the automation of many medical centers and pharmacies, and a sufficiently high level of informing the population has been established. At the same time, in the last 3-5 years, a large number of new commercial medical institutions have appeared in which automation is carried out "from scratch". On the one hand, these factors create favorable conditions for the introduction of ICT in the field of medical services and the provision of medicines, on the other hand, they require a very fine maneuvering between the need to promote the maximum dissemination of medical information and the need to introduce certain restrictions on access to it for persons who do not have sufficient qualifications. For an adequate assessment of this information, not to mention control over the dissemination of false information and unscrupulous advertising of methods of treatment and medicines[3].

The most important areas for the introduction of ICT in the field of healthcare include the following:

- creation of a unified information database "Electronic health passport of a citizen";
- creation of a computer database with detailed information on medicines and medical devices - for the population and for specialists;
- providing access to medical information for professional users and consumers of relevant goods and services;
- training of the personnel of each health care institution of the country in the skills of working with e-mail and Internet resources with a mandatory examination of knowledge during the certification period.
- creation on the basis of leading institutes, clinics and diagnostic centers of "consultation via the Internet" points for all healthcare institutions, including polyclinics, as well as a system for registering the population with specialists via e-mail[4].

The inevitable introduction of ICT into all spheres of life dictates a new strategy for reforming and modernizing health care. At the same time, it is important that the costs of implementing the reform do not burden the budget, because otherwise, they will remain on paper. One of the components of this approach is "electronic medicine".

E-medicine is understood as a set of procedures that provides, with the help of ICT and high-speed backbone communication channels, an adequate exchange of medical data at a distance.

This direction is developing rapidly, doctors of Uzbekistan are also included in various national and international projects. So a number of clinical centers in Tashkent and Samarkand carry out electronic medical contacts with clinics in the USA, Germany and India [5].

Plastic cards, electronic bracelets in hospitals, electronic medical records should be widely used[6]. It will be possible to introduce typical integrated applications for medical institutions and browsers for patient access[7].

One of the primary tasks is the creation of automated systems for storing and accessing graphic information and information on the availability of donor material, as well as providing services for interpreting the results of examinations and organizing an electronic queue for donor material. However, despite the fact that at present the basic principles of e-health have already been approved, the concept of its construction is not sufficiently developed and is not being implemented, and the regulatory framework is practically absent .

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